

1 **ATP6V1B1 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the ATPase H⁺ transporting V1 subunit B1, ATP6V1B1, was
14 among those whose expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing total
15 transcription between tumor and normal brain tissue. ATP6V1B1 expression levels were significantly
16 increased in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain. ATP6V1B1 function at the
17 systems level was assessed by studying whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the
18 transformed brain. ATP6V1B1 is a target of interest for the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a
19 rationally designed chemotherapeutic regimen that utilizes gene expression data from patient tumors and
20 healthy non-transformed tissues to maximize efficacy and safety and minimize toxicity.

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26 Keywords: ATP6V1B1, ATPase H⁺ transporting V1 subunit B1, glioblastoma, systems biology of
27 glioblastoma, targeted therapeutics in glioblastoma.

Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole transcriptome methods.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional co-regulation studies (8).

Results

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6) to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

ATP6V1B1 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1812073	8.43E-06	-5.080545	3.244075	-1.07265171	ATP6V1B1	4632/47229	90.2

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of ATPase H⁺ transporting V1 subunit B1, encoded by ATP6V1B1 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of ATP6V1B1 changed more than 90% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change

1 indicating increased quantity of ATP6V1B1 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating
 2 up-regulation of ATP6V1B1 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

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 4 2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

5 $n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

6 $n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

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ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
525	9.10E-06	0.978	-4.4375113	-4.33839611	66.28	ATP6V1B1	1133/19678	99.3

8

9 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
 10 tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort,
 11 we validated differential expression of ATP6V1B1 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression
 12 of ATP6V1B1 here changed more than 99% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when
 13 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”).
 Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ATP6V1B1 messenger RNA in
 glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of ATP6V1B1 during transformation of the brain from
 normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

14 Thus, ATP6V1B1 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the
 glioblastoma subtype in humans.

15
 16 ATP6V1B1 transcriptional co-regulation.

17 Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to
 18 provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within
 19 which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

27 In the transformed brain, ATP6V1B1 was transcriptionally co-regulated with DOT1L, SETDB1,
 28 RARA, GPC2, ZNF496 and ZNF219.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 ATP6V1B1 as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level
3 query into ATP6V1B1 molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its
4 co-regulation with DOT1L, SETDB1, RARA, GPC2, ZNF496 and ZNF219.

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 ATPase H⁺ transporting V1 subunit B1, ATP6V1B1, was among the genes most differentially expressed in
7 the primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; ATP6V1B1 was expressed at significantly higher levels
8 in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. ATP6V1B1 is a target of interest for rationally designed
9 medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
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